

MASTER CLASS - ONE OF THE FORMS OF EFFECTIVE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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A master class is an interactive form of learning and exchange of experience, combining the format of a training and a conference. A master class is a special genre for disseminating successful work experience based on an original author's methodology. A master class in pedagogy is close to an open lesson; it implies active participation in one form or another of the adult audience present. Three main types of pedagogical master classes are distinguished.

Presentation of teaching experience: the main ideas of the presented educational or upbringing technology are briefly described, a visual example of work is demonstrated (in the form of a lesson or extracurricular activity); problems and prospects in the work of a teacher are discussed with the audience (in fact, such a master class is an open lesson without a time limit, conducted in a free form).

Modeling: teacher participants perform independent work on constructing their own model of a lesson in the mode of the lesson technology proposed by the specialist. The specialist conducting the master class acts as a consultant; he only organizes the independent activity of the audience, and then participates in the discussion of the author's models created during the lesson (this option is closest to the classic master class).

Simulation game: the teacher conducts a training session with listeners who take the place of students, playing two roles at the same time: students and experts present at an open lesson.

Purpose of research: to create a means of mastering the methodology of innovations in the professional sphere, joint development of the methodological approaches of the master teacher and methods of solving the problem posed in the master class program.

The tasks: the transfer of the master teacher's experience through a direct and commented demonstration of the sequence of actions, methods, techniques and forms of pedagogical activity, the transfer of the master teacher's experience through a direct and commented demonstration of the sequence of actions, methods, techniques and forms of pedagogical activity.

The topics of the master classes include: an overview of current issues and technologies, various aspects and techniques for using technologies, original methods for applying technologies in practice, etc.

Master class technology algorithm: presentation of pedagogical experience by a master teacher, presentation of a system of educational classes, conducting a simulation game, modeling, reflection.

During the master class, participants: study developments on the topic of the master class; participate in the discussion of the results obtained; ask questions, receive consultations. The main thing in the technology of conducting a master class is not to communicate and master information, but to convey methods of activity, be it a technique, method, methodology or technology.

Conclusions: thus, to convey productive ways of working is one of the most important tasks for the Master. The relevance and scientific nature of the content and methods of teaching, the presence of new ideas that go beyond the standard and correspond to the trends of modern education and the methodology of teaching the subject, the ability not only to methodologically, but also to scientifically generalize experience

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